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safe and flexible CCUS

Retrofitting Amine CO₂ Capture to a WtE plant

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About ACCSESS

If CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) is to become a relevant, large-scale technology for cutting carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, several barriers need to be addressed, and its deployment must be accelerated.

ACCSESS works to address key challenges to the successful implementation of CCS across Europe: namely, challenges related to CO₂ capture, CCS chains, and societal acceptance. The project focuses on four industrial sectors with the potential to drastically reduce CO₂ emissions by implementing CCS: waste-to-energy, pulp and paper, cement, and biorefineries.

ACCSESS started in May 2021. Its consortium consists of 18 partners from eight different European countries.

www.projectaccess.eu

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Klemetsrud WtE inside the plant. Image courtesy: Kinect Energy Group

About this document:

This document outlines a possible approach to retrofitting Waste to Energy (WtE) plants with Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS), encapsulated in the concept of 'Neutral Solution Packages' (NSP). The 'Neutral' in NSP reflects its design for broad applicability across diverse urban contexts, without being tied to a specific site. 'Solution' indicates a strategic response that effectively tackles the challenges in the given context, while 'Package' conveys the comprehensive and all-inclusive nature of the guidelines. Designed for city administrators and urban planners, the document serves to facilitate the understanding and adoption of CCS in WtE facilities, highlighting the critical role of CCS in driving urban carbon reduction efforts.

Description:

Retrofitting a CCS system to an existing WtE plant presents complex challenges but also an opportunity to reduce carbon emissions. WtE plants process substantial amounts of waste and can contribute significantly to urban CO₂ emissions. By implementing CCS, these plants can become significant contributors to CO₂ emission reductions.

Challenges/Goal:

The primary goal of this NSP is to highlight the complexities and critical factors associated with retrofitting CO₂ capture to an existing WtE facility. This will facilitate a better understanding of the risks and challenges associated with such a complex endeavour and

ultimately contribute to the development of sustainable and efficient carbon capture solutions in the WtE industry.

Challenges and solutions:

Retrofitting CO₂ capture to an existing and fully operational WtE plant introduces significant challenges, including:

1. Plot Area Restrictions:

- Challenge: Many WtE incineration plants are located in urban areas with limited available space for expansion. Implementing CO₂ capture (including processing captured CO₂ for transport) on site will require space. Height restrictions for CO₂ capture process components can also be a concern.
- Solution: During the early planning stages, it is crucial to consider extensive margins for the CCS technology. This involves anticipating not only the space required for the CO₂ capture and processing itself but also the space for construction and lay-down areas. Furthermore, negotiating framework agreements for land acquisition or lease before investment decisions can help ensure availability and control over the required space. Ideally, this should be done before moving into the detailed engineering phase.

2. Transport Infrastructure:

- Challenge: Securing the necessary transport infrastructure for liquefied CO₂ shipment by e.g. trucks or ships, especially if the project is located near congested areas or if the ports are not big enough for the required vessels and its added traffic, it can be complex and expensive. Although, the proximity to a port can be an advantage if the beforementioned challenges can be overcome.
- Solution: To mitigate this challenge, it is advisable to secure agreements for plots and transportation solutions, such as port access, during the preliminary planning phase. Waiting until the project is in the execution phase can increase risks and costs.

3. Coordination with WtE Plant Logistics:

- Challenge: The retrofitting of CCS can disrupt the logistics of the existing WtE plant, affecting the handling, maintenance, and safety systems of the waste trucks.
- Solution: Conducting a logistics mapping during the early stages of planning can help identify the specific needs and requirements of the WtE plant. Furthermore, future expansion plans for the WtE plant should be considered, as these can be integrated more effectively when CCS is retrofitted. Engaging in a master planning process for the entire plant, including the CCS, can improve overall efficiency.

4. Complex Groundworks:

- Challenge: Extending the plot for CCS construction involves extensive groundwork, including potentially disruptive activities such as blasting and excavation.
- Solution: To address this challenge, it is crucial to conduct a detailed front-end engineering design (FEED) study for ground works before the execution of the project. This study can help assess the scope of the groundwork required and identify potential issues. A survey of sub-ground infrastructure, such as utility lines, should also be carried out during the preliminary planning phases.

5. Efficient Use of Steam and Heat Recovery:

- Challenge: WtE plants typically produce steam and/or hot water from incineration for electricity and district heating. Implementing CCS can reduce the production of electricity and district heating.
- Potential solution: Address this challenge by installing a heat recovery system, such as a heat pump, to regenerate heat from the CO₂ capture process and redirect it to the district heating system. Evaluate feasibility, considering initial investment and long-term energy savings.

6. Power supply to CCS:

- Challenge: Meeting the electricity demand of CO₂ capture and processing may require substantial upgrades to local power grids, which can introduce delays and risks. It is important to note that a significant portion of this energy demand is associated with operating a heat pump for heat recovery if one is implemented.
- Solution: To manage this challenge, include design margins for electricity consumption in the FEED study. If the local grid cannot provide sufficient power, consider this a major project risk, as building new infrastructure can be time-consuming. Evaluating power grid capacity early on is crucial.

7. Wastewater handling:

- Challenge: Reducing the temperature of the flue gas before the CO₂ capture can lead to increased condensed water production, necessitating local wastewater treatment, which can be costly and space intensive. Furthermore, this water must undergo treatment at both the local wastewater treatment plant for the CO₂ capture plant and subsequently at the municipal wastewater treatment facility, incurring additional expenses.
- Solution: Address wastewater treatment requirements during the FEED phase, incorporating safety factors for flows, volumes, and footprint. Ensure that all necessary permits for additional wastewater volumes are obtained from local authorities.

8. Constructability:

- Challenge: Transporting large, workshop-built structures to an urban construction site can be challenging, often resulting in more costly stick-built constructions.
- Solution: Conduct an early transport survey to define the feasibility of transporting large components from the nearest port to the WtE plant. Evaluate the cost implications of extending the plot versus dealing with complex transport logistics.

Technology components:

Amine-based carbon capture technology can be used in WtE plants. This process uses amine technology to selectively absorb CO₂, resulting in a combustion gas stream with reduced CO₂ content. This captured CO₂ can then be transported and safely stored. To retrofit a WtE plant with amine-based carbon capture technology, certain preconditions must be met, including considerations for overall efficiency, minimising false air intake, and accommodating additional space requirements. The WtE plant must also be equipped to provide the necessary amine solution for the carbon capture process. The key components of a retrofitted WtE plant for amine-based carbon capture include the following.

- **Amine solution supply system:** Provide the amine technology and solution for the carbon capture process. There are currently several vendors in the market offering amine-based CO₂ capture technologies at the process scale required for WtE plants. The technology includes the flue gas treatment setup: comprising equipment for CO₂ absorption and subsequent release.
- **CO₂ Compression and Purification Unit (CPU):** Purifying and preparing the captured CO₂ for storage (or use).

Implementation Process:

Feasibility Assessment: A feasibility study of the CO₂ capture retrofit to the WtE plant is necessary to understand the cost effectiveness and technological feasibility.

Corresponding timeline for early movers based on interviews conducted with the relevant stakeholders:

Stage	Timeline (Months)
Feasibility Study	5 to 7
Regulatory Compliance Assessment	3 to 5
Engineering and Design	10 to 14
Permitting and Approvals	10 to 14 ¹
Procurement	10 to 14
Implementation Phase	12 to 24
Construction and Integration	20 to 28
Commissioning and Testing	4 to 7
Training and Workforce Development	12 to 14
Overall	60

Regulations and laws:

- **Environmental Permits:** Obtain permits for air emissions, waste management, and Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA).
- **Emissions Limits:** Adherence to emission limit values for pollutants.
- **CO₂ storage licencing:** secure licences for the geological storage of captured CO₂, this is typically done through an agreement with a CO₂ transport and storage operator.

Since WtE plants are often located in densely populated urban areas, additional emission permits are required. An environmental hazard identification and qualitative risk assessment have to be carried out, as well as risk and vulnerability analysis prepared. In the case of use of amine-based solution, there is a direct contact with the flue gas and thus emissions could get released into the atmosphere. To evaluate the risk related to amine emissions, dispersion analysis can be a part of the emission permit application. It addresses both air quality and drinking water guidelines, thus, assuring the environmental and health safety in the area.

¹ This is dependent on the country where the retrofitting takes place.

Citizen Engagement:

Effective citizen engagement involves educating and involving the local community in the CCS retrofitting process. This includes transparent communication about the benefits and impacts of CCS on local environments and emission reduction goals. The approach should aim to address common concerns, provide clear answers to frequently asked questions, and involve citizens in discussions and decision-making processes. Workshops, public forums, and information campaigns can be valuable tools for raising awareness and garnering support.

Advice for replication:

- **Engage local stakeholders:** Start by working with local government departments, waste management teams, and relevant technology providers. Collaborative efforts are key.
- **Site-Specific Design:** Customise the solution to meet the existing infrastructure and energy needs of our municipal WtE facility.
- **Feasibility analysis:** Conduct a thorough analysis of your local district heating demand, climatic conditions, and regulatory requirements. This will help you determine the most suitable setup.
- **Selection of technology:** Choose the carbon capture technology that aligns with the goals of our municipality, considering factors such as efficiency, size, and compliance with local regulations.
- **Compliance Assurance:** Ensure that the implementation is consistent with your municipality's waste incineration regulations and environmental standards.
- **Financial Planning:** Develop a financial plan that outlines the initial investment, operational costs, and possible financial support from regional or national organisations.
- **Community Engagement:** Engage actively with members of your community and local stakeholders. Building awareness and support for sustainable waste management and emission reduction is vital.
- **Performance monitoring:** Implement a monitoring system to track performance over time after implementation of the CO₂ capture technology is in operation. This will help assess impact on reducing carbon emissions and improving energy efficiency.

Addressed SDGs:

Media files and further reading:

Title	Author	Year	Link
CCS Retrofit Analysis Report	International Energy Agency (IEA)	2012	CCS retrofit - Analysis – IEA
Waste-to-energy technology integrated with carbon capture: Challenges and opportunities.	P. Wienchol et al.	2020	ELSEVIER - WtE technology
Modelling and assessing the integration of CO ₂ capture and waste-to-energy plants delivering district heating	Tuvshinjargal Otgonbayar, Marco Mazzotti	2024	ELSEVIER - Modelling and assessing the integration of CO₂ capture in –WtE Plants
Fortum Oslo Varme AS applies for the establishment of a carbon capture plant	Norwegian Environment Agency	2021	Fortum Oslo Varme applies for carbon capture plant - Norwegian Environment Agency (miljodirektoratet.no)
Dispersion and deposition modelling NO ₂ , nitrosamines and nitramines, for emission permit application	Fortum Oslo Varme AS	2020	Dispersion Report